

Philippine English: A Quantitative Study on Undergraduate Language Students' Attitude from a Non-Metropolitan Teacher Higher Education Institution

¹Nurhaliza Nayic^{ORCID}, ²Abnir T. Arilin^{ORCID}, ³Alprince King A. Biri^{ORCID}

¹Carl Balita Review Center, ²Universidad de Zamboanga, ³Ateneo de Zamboanga University

¹nurhalizanayic@gmail.com, ²abnirarilin5@gmail.com, ³alprincekingabdulabiri@gmail.com,

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Corresponding Email:
abnirarilin5@gmail.com

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Abstract. This study examined the attitudes of undergraduate language students toward Philippine English (PhE) in a non-metropolitan teacher education institution. Specifically, it explored students' attitudes across four dimensions—experiences, observations, perspectives, and future recommendations—and assessed their acceptance of selected PhE grammatical and lexical features. A quantitative descriptive survey design was employed, involving 52 Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English students selected through convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire with a 4-point Likert scale and analyzed using weighted mean and standard deviation. The findings revealed that students generally hold favorable attitudes toward Philippine English. Respondents reported regular use of PhE in both academic and everyday contexts and perceived it as widely used within their environment. Students strongly recognized PhE as a legitimate variety of English and associated it with Filipino identity, while also expressing comfort in its use and interest in its inclusion in formal instruction. However, a relatively moderate level of agreement was observed regarding its broader application beyond local or educational contexts. In terms of linguistic features, most PhE grammatical and lexical items were accepted, although respondents demonstrated selectivity by showing lower agreement toward less conventional or highly informal forms. These results suggest that Philippine English is both functionally embedded and socially valued among future educators, while still subject to considerations of appropriateness and context. The study highlights the importance of addressing localized language varieties in teacher education and provides insights into how language attitudes may influence future instructional practices.

Introduction

English has become a dominant global language widely used in academia, business, and international communication. As noted by Mahana et al. (2019), English functions as a primary medium of communication across diverse sectors, and its use continues to expand worldwide. This global spread has led to the development of multiple localized varieties collectively referred to as World Englishes (WE), which include well-established forms such as American English (AmE), British English, and other institutionalized varieties used in both native and non-native contexts.

Attitudes toward language play a crucial role in shaping language use, acceptance, and policy. Attitude is generally defined as an evaluation or assessment of an object, idea, or phenomenon (Bohner & Wanke, 2002), although it is not directly observable (Lanos, 2014). From a psychological perspective, Ajzen and Fishbein (1977) describe attitude as an evaluative disposition directed toward specific objects, which Ricohermoso, Abequibel, and Alieto (2019) refer to as the "attitudinal object." This conceptualization is further supported by the Mentalist Theory, which explains that attitudes are internally

constructed and manifested through observable responses (Somblino & Alieto, 2019). Given the abstract nature of attitudes, scholars have developed various instruments to measure language attitudes across different contexts (Jacinto & Alieto, 2020), highlighting their importance in understanding linguistic preferences and behaviors.

The Philippines is situated within the "outer circle" of World Englishes, where English serves as a second language and plays a central role in education, governance, and professional communication. As explained by Esquivel (2019), the widespread use of English in the Philippines can be traced back to American colonization, during which English was institutionalized as the primary medium of instruction. Over time, this prolonged exposure led to the development of a localized variety known as Philippine English (PhE), which reflects the linguistic, cultural, and social realities of Filipino speakers. Ong (2020) further emphasizes that PhE functions as an established second-language variety actively used in various domains across the country.

Despite its widespread use, the integration of Philippine English into the formal education curriculum remains a subject of ongoing debate. Applied linguistics and English language education continue to grapple with questions regarding the legitimacy, standardization, and pedagogical inclusion of emerging English varieties. While PhE has gained recognition as a distinct variety, uncertainties persist regarding its acceptance as a medium of instruction and its role in shaping language education policies.

Previous studies have primarily focused on the attitudes of English teachers and graduate students toward Philippine English. For instance, Bautista (2001) reported positive attitudes among English language faculty in leading Philippine universities, while Alieto and Rillo (2018) found similar results among English teachers in both public and private schools. Hernandez (2020) further demonstrated that graduate students from a premier teacher education institution expressed favorable attitudes toward the teaching of educated Philippine English. In addition, Borlongan (2009) revealed that undergraduate students perceived PhE as a marker of Filipino identity and expressed no hesitation in using it in communication. These studies consistently suggest a generally positive orientation toward Philippine English across different groups.

The development of Philippine English is closely tied to the historical and sociolinguistic context of the country. Since the American occupation, English has been institutionalized as a medium of instruction and widely used across domains, leading to its recognition as the Philippines' second language (Esquivel, 2019). Prolonged exposure to English in education, governance, and media has resulted in the emergence of a localized variety shaped by Filipino linguistic and cultural influences. This evolution reflects how language adapts to its users, positioning Philippine English as both a functional communication tool and a marker of identity within the broader framework of World Englishes.

However, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding undergraduate students, particularly those in teacher education programs who are future language educators. While some studies have included undergraduate participants, limited research has specifically examined their attitudes in non-metropolitan teacher education institutions. Understanding the perspectives of this group is critical, as their attitudes may influence future instructional practices and decisions regarding language use in educational settings.

Teachers play a pivotal role in shaping learners' linguistic attitudes and behaviors. As emphasized by Ulug et al. (2011), teachers' methods, attitudes, and behaviors significantly influence students' development, including their perspectives toward language use. Similarly, Malureanu (2021) highlights that teachers contribute to learners' personal and academic growth, serving as role models whose influence extends beyond the classroom. In the context of language education, this underscores the importance of examining the attitudes of future educators, as their beliefs may directly affect instructional practices and language choices in educational settings.

Furthermore, attitudes toward Philippine English among educators and learners have been widely examined, with consistently positive findings. Bautista (2001) reported favorable attitudes among English faculty in leading universities, while Alieto and Rillo (2018) found similar results among high school teachers. Hernandez (2020) also demonstrated that graduate students expressed positive attitudes toward the teaching of educated Philippine English. Among undergraduates, Borlongan (2009) found that students perceive Philippine English as a symbol of Filipino identity and exhibit confidence in using it. Collectively, these studies indicate a general acceptance of Philippine English across different groups, although variations in context and population suggest the need for further investigation.

Given this gap, the present study aims to investigate the attitudes of undergraduate language students toward Philippine English across four dimensions: experiences, observations, perspectives, and future recommendations. Additionally, this study seeks to determine whether these students agree with existing Philippine English grammatical and lexical features.

This study is anchored in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) proposed by Ajzen (1991), which explains how attitudes influence behavioral intentions and actual behavior. The theory posits that an individual's behavior is shaped by three key components: attitudes toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Within the context of language use, attitudes toward a specific language variety—such as Philippine English—can influence individuals' willingness to use, accept, or promote that variety in academic and professional settings. In this study, the positive or negative evaluations of undergraduate language students toward Philippine English are assumed to shape their future intentions as educators, particularly in decisions related to language use in instruction and curriculum integration. Thus, examining students' attitudes provides insight into potential behavioral outcomes in language teaching practices. In addition, this study draws on the Mentalist Theory of Attitude, which conceptualizes attitude as an internal psychological state that cannot be directly observed but can be inferred through measurable responses (Somblingo & Alieto, 2019). This perspective aligns with earlier conceptualizations of attitude as an evaluative disposition toward an attitudinal object (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1977; Bohner & Wanke, 2002). Since attitudes are latent constructs, they are typically assessed through structured instruments such as Likert-scale questionnaires (Jacinto & Alieto, 2020). In the present study, students' attitudes toward Philippine English are operationalized through four dimensions—experiences, observations, perspectives, and future recommendations—allowing for a quantifiable representation of their internal evaluations. By combining the Mentalist perspective with quantitative measurement, the study is able to systematically capture and analyze language attitudes in a way that reflects both psychological theory and empirical methodology.

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative descriptive survey design to examine the attitudes of undergraduate language students toward Philippine English. Quantitative research involves the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data to describe trends, relationships, or patterns (Creswell, 2002). The use of a survey design was appropriate for this study, as it allowed for the measurement of students' attitudes across predefined dimensions, including experiences, observations, perspectives, and future recommendations. This approach enabled the researcher to obtain measurable and comparable data reflecting the respondents' evaluative positions toward Philippine English.

The participants of the study consisted of 52 undergraduate students enrolled in the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English at a teacher education institution. The respondents were selected using convenience sampling, based on their accessibility and willingness to participate. The sample included students from different year levels, providing a range of perspectives within the program. While this sampling technique allowed for efficient data collection, it may limit the generalizability of the findings; thus, the results should be interpreted within the context of the selected participants.

Data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire composed of three parts. Part A gathered basic demographic information without collecting personally identifiable data. Part B consisted of fifteen (15) attitudinal statements developed by the researcher to measure students' attitudes toward Philippine English across four dimensions: experiences, observations, perspectives, and future recommendations. Part C included items on Philippine English grammatical and lexical features adopted from Alieto and Torres (2019). The questionnaire utilized a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). Prior to data collection, the instrument was reviewed to ensure content relevance and clarity of items in relation to the study objectives.

The data were collected through an online survey administered via Google Forms, with an average completion time of approximately 15 minutes. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents before they proceeded with the survey. The data were encoded and analyzed using Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistical measures, including weighted mean and standard deviation, were employed to summarize and interpret the responses. These statistical techniques were appropriate for analyzing ordinal data derived from Likert-scale items and for identifying general trends in students' attitudes toward Philippine English. The study adhered to established ethical standards for research involving human participants. Informed consent was obtained prior to participation, and respondents' anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained, with all data used solely for academic purposes.

Results and Discussion

Language Students' Profile

A total of 52 undergraduate students participated in the study, all of whom were enrolled in the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English. The respondents were distributed across different year levels, including 13 first-year students, 17 second-year students, 13 third-year students, and 9 fourth-year students. This distribution reflects a representation of students at varying stages of their academic training, allowing for a broader perspective on attitudes toward Philippine English within the program.

Language Students' Experience on Philippine English

The results indicate that undergraduate language students generally demonstrate positive engagement with Philippine English in both academic and everyday contexts. As shown in Table 1, respondents reported that they often use Philippine English in daily conversations (M = 3.19, SD = 0.68), participate in class discussions using Philippine English (M = 3.05, SD = 0.74), and are encouraged by their teachers to use Philippine English when they are unable to express their thoughts in standard English (M = 3.13, SD = 0.85). All items fall within the "Agree" range, suggesting a consistent level of acceptance and usage across different situations.

#	Items	Mean	SD	Interpretation
2	I often speak using Philippine English in daily conversations.	3.19	0.68	
7	We are encouraged by our teachers to speak in Philippine English if we could not express our thoughts in standard English.	3.13	0.85	Agree
6	I use Philippine English when participating in class discussions.	3.05	0.74	

Scale: 1.0-1.74 Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.4 Disagree; 2.5-3.24 Agree; 3.25-4.0 Strongly Agree

Table 1: Experience with Philippine English

Overall, the findings suggest that Philippine English is not only recognized but also actively practiced by students in both informal and formal settings. The consistent agreement across items indicates that exposure to and use of Philippine English are already embedded in students' linguistic experiences, particularly within classroom environments where flexibility in language use is permitted.

Language Students' Observation on Philippine English

The findings indicate that respondents perceive Philippine English as a commonly used language variety in their environment. As presented in Table 2, students reported that Philippine English is used more frequently than American English (M = 3.17, SD = 0.72), which falls within the "Agree" range. This suggests that students are consistently exposed to Philippine English in both academic and social contexts.

#	Items	Mean	SD	Interpretation
5	I observed that Philippine English is used more often than American English.	3.19	0.68	Agree

Scale: 1.0-1.74 Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.4 Disagree; 2.5-3.24 Agree; 3.25-4.0 Strongly Agree

Table 2: Observations of Philippine English

The result implies that Philippine English has a strong presence in the linguistic landscape of the respondents, reinforcing its role as a functional and widely utilized variety of English in the Philippines. Such exposure may contribute to students' familiarity with and acceptance of Philippine English, as reflected in their overall positive attitudes observed in subsequent sections.

Language Students' Personal Perspective Toward Philippine English

The results reveal a strongly positive orientation of undergraduate language students toward Philippine English. As presented in Table 3, respondents strongly agree that Philippine English is a legitimate variety of the English language (M = 3.55, SD = 0.53) and that speaking in Philippine English is not rude (M = 3.51, SD = 0.49). Additionally, students express a sense of pride in using Philippine English (M = 3.42, SD = 0.56) and recognize it as a symbol of Filipino identity (M = 3.25, SD = 0.75), both of which fall within the "Strongly Agree" range. Other items, including comfort in using Philippine English (M = 3.21, SD = 0.59) and willingness to learn it in formal instruction (M = 3.21, SD = 0.66), fall under the "Agree" category. These results indicate that while students strongly affirm the legitimacy and social value of Philippine English, their personal usage and learning intentions, although positive, are slightly less pronounced.

#	Items	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	I recognize Philippine English as a legitimate variety of English Language.	3.55	0.53	
11	Speaking in Philippine English is not rude.	3.51	0.49	Strongly Agree
4	I feel proud when I speak in Philippine English.	3.42	0.56	
14	Philippine English is a Filipino pride, a symbol of Filipino identity.	3.25	0.75	
3	I am comfortable in communicating with Philippine English.	3.21	0.59	Agree

8	I want to learn Philippine English in our English language class.	3.21	0.66
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Scale: 1.0-1.74 Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.4 Disagree; 2.5-3.24 Agree; 3.25-4.0 Strongly Agree

Table 3: Perspectives toward Philippine English

Overall, the findings demonstrate that students not only accept Philippine English as a valid linguistic variety but also associate it with cultural identity and personal expression, reinforcing its relevance in both communicative and educational contexts.

Language Students' Recommendations Toward Philippine English

The findings indicate that students generally support the inclusion and development of Philippine English in educational contexts, although with varying levels of agreement. As shown in Table 4, respondents strongly agree that Philippine English should be integrated into the school curriculum (M = 3.26, SD = 0.65) and that other varieties of English should also be included (M = 3.25, SD = 0.70). Moreover, students express agreement that digital forms of Philippine English may be incorporated into instruction (M = 3.19, SD = 0.65), a standardized grammatical framework should be established (M = 3.11, SD = 0.72), and that Philippine English should be used as a primary means of communication both within and beyond the country obtained the lowest mean (M = 2.75, SD = 0.39), although it still falls within the "Agree" range. This indicates a comparatively more cautious stance among students regarding the broader, global use of Philippine English.

#	Items	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	I suggest that Philippine English should be integrated into the school curricula.	3.26	0.65	Strongly Agree
11	I suggest that we should integrate other variety of English language into the school curricula.	3.25	0.70	
4	Digitalized Philippine English should also be taught in schools.	3.19	0.65	Agree
14	The authorities should implement a grammatical standard for Philippine English.	3.11	0.72	
3	Philippine English should be the language used by Filipinos in communicating within and beyond the country.	2.75	0.39	

Scale: 1.0-1.74 Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.4 Disagree; 2.5-3.24 Agree; 3.25-4.0 Strongly Agree

Table 4: Future Recommendations for Philippine English

Overall, the results suggest that while students are supportive of the institutional integration and development of Philippine English, they exhibit a more moderate level of agreement when it comes to its wider application beyond local or educational contexts.

Finally, the results in the lexical items were arranged from highest to lowest in rank. The results indicate that respondents generally accept the majority of Philippine English grammatical and lexical features, with most items falling within the "Agree" to "Strongly Agree" ranges. Several items received relatively higher levels of agreement, including statements such as "Majority of students nowadays use online references to do their papers" (M = 3.42, SD = 0.56), "Many classic movies are based from popular novels" (M = 3.38, SD = 0.59), and "Failure to return borrowed books... can result to fines" (M = 3.36, SD = 0.62), all of which fall under "Strongly Agree."

A substantial number of items were rated within the "Agree" range, indicating general acceptability of commonly used Philippine English expressions in academic and everyday contexts. These include constructions such as "cope up with," "in behalf of," and "unfriended me," suggesting that respondents are familiar with and receptive to localized linguistic forms. However, a small number of items were rated under "Disagree," including expressions such as "unsmile," "OMGed," and "xeroxed," which represent less conventional or more informal linguistic formations. These results suggest that while students generally accept Philippine English, they may be more selective when it comes to nonstandard or highly informal lexical innovations.

#	Items	Mean	SD	Interpretation
11	Majority of students nowadays use online references to do their papers.	3.42	0.56	Strongly Agree
2	Many classic movies are based from popular novels.	3.38	0.59	Strongly Agree
1	Failure to return borrowed books from the library on time can result to fines and other penalties.	3.36	0.62	Strongly Agree
35	I will return next week.	3.34	0.55	Strongly Agree
36	The celebrant did not expect the kind of party given to him.	3.30	0.57	Strongly Agree
5	Students should learn to cope up with the challenges in their studies.	3.30	0.57	Strongly Agree
42	He will bring his father to Tagaytay this summer.	3.25	0.58	Strongly Agree

12	It must be enacted to a law whatever the political cost .	3.23	0.57	Agree
13	They left the Philippines before their children entered college.	3.23	0.66	Agree
16	The number of students enrolled last term have increased.	3.21	0.66	Agree
7	There are a number of organizations wherein students can join.	3.19	0.65	Agree
6	Students have different views with regards success.	3.17	0.69	Agree
23	The president assured free tuition to all State Universities and Colleges.	3.15	0.60	Agree
10	The secretary attended the meeting in behalf of her boss.	3.15	0.69	Agree
15	The use of social media have been the most significant change in the last decade.	3.11	0.57	Agree
17	A number of different teaching techniques has emerged.	3.11	0.80	Agree
39	She tried to quickly finish the book before she had to leave.	3.05	0.66	Agree
20	This method, along with other methods, are applicable now.	3.03	0.85	Agree
9	Students should get involved to extra-curricular activities.	3.01	0.77	Agree
25	Due to the requirements, me and my groupmates are staying in the hostel over the weekend.	2.98	0.79	Agree
21	I, together with my other classmate, are attending the symposium.	2.96	0.83	Agree
43	Faculty members are engaged in their respective researches .	2.96	0.85	Agree
4	During quizzes, students are asked to fill the blanks.	2.90	0.79	Agree
26	In pair work, choose the person who you think you could work well with.	2.94	0.81	Agree
41	My doctor advised me to have less doughnut for my immediate recovery.	2.94	0.90	Agree
38	The five members divided the task between themselves.	2.92	0.97	Agree
30	Since I was not responding to his message, he unfriended me in Facebook.	2.90	0.76	Agree
28	Thank you for the invite you sent last week.	2.90	0.86	Agree
14	Students are required to attend the symposium which would be held in May.	2.88	0.82	Agree
18	Either the students or the teacher know how to open the presentation.	2.86	0.80	Agree
22	That is one of the reason why I chose to pursue my education.	2.86	0.98	Agree
8	It's a more correct answer.	2.82	0.87	Agree
19	One-third of the test items was asked during the review.	2.82	0.95	Agree
27	Since its very traffic in Metro Manila, I don't want to study there.	2.69	0.88	Agree
40	I should drink fewer coffee.	2.69	0.99	Agree
29	My teacher has that fascination in vintagy items.	2.65	0.95	Agree
32	I have PMed to you the proposal.	2.59	0.98	Agree
37	This is necessarily needed to pass the course.	2.53	1.02	Agree
44	Last February 14, I did a not so valentiney undertaking.	2.50	1.08	Agree
24	In schools, students taken cared of by their teachers.	2.48	1.10	Disagree
34	The materials were already xeroxed yesterday.	2.40	1.09	Disagree
33	When he heard the news, he OMGed .	2.46	1.04	Disagree
3	My perspective is sometimes different for your perspective.	2.38	1.09	Disagree
31	He would unsmile whenever that person passes by.	2.15	0.94	Disagree

Scale: 1.0-1.74 Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.4 Disagree; 2.5-3.24 Agree; 3.25-4.0 Strongly Agree

Table 5: Philippine English Grammatical and Lexical Terms

Overall, the findings demonstrate that respondents exhibit a broad but not indiscriminate acceptance of Philippine English grammatical and lexical features, favoring commonly used and contextually appropriate expressions over less conventional forms.

The findings of the study indicate that undergraduate language students demonstrate a generally positive orientation toward Philippine English across experiential, perceptual, and evaluative dimensions. The consistent agreement observed in students' reported experiences suggests that Philippine English is not only recognized but also routinely used in both academic and informal contexts. This aligns with the notion that language attitudes are shaped through repeated exposure and social interaction, reinforcing the idea that familiarity contributes to acceptance. The observed patterns support the view that Philippine English functions as a practical linguistic resource rather than merely a theoretical construct within the framework of World Englishes.

From a theoretical perspective, the results can be interpreted through the lens of the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), which posits that attitudes influence behavioral intentions. The generally favorable attitudes toward Philippine English observed in this study suggest a potential inclination among future educators to incorporate or tolerate its use in

instructional settings. This is particularly relevant given that respondents are pre-service teachers whose beliefs may translate into classroom practices. In parallel, the Mentalist Theory of Attitude (Somblingo & Alieto, 2019) provides further support by framing attitudes as internal evaluative states that manifest through observable responses, such as agreement with attitudinal statements. The measured responses across the four dimensions reflect these internal evaluations, offering empirical insight into how Philippine English is cognitively and socially positioned by the respondents.

The strong endorsement of Philippine English as a legitimate language variety, coupled with its association with Filipino identity, is consistent with prior research. Studies by Bautista (2001), Alieto and Rillo (2018), and Hernandez (2020) similarly reported positive attitudes among educators and graduate students, while Borlongan (2009) highlighted its role as a marker of identity among undergraduates. The present findings extend these results by confirming that such positive orientations are also evident among students in a non-metropolitan teacher education context. This suggests that acceptance of Philippine English is not limited to elite or urban academic environments but may be more broadly distributed across different educational settings.

Despite this generally positive orientation, variations in the level of agreement across items provide a more nuanced perspective. While students strongly affirm the legitimacy and social value of Philippine English, their agreement is comparatively moderate when it comes to its expanded use beyond local or educational contexts. This pattern may reflect an awareness of the continued dominance of standardized or internationally recognized English varieties in global communication. Similarly, in the evaluation of grammatical and lexical items, respondents tend to accept commonly used and contextually appropriate expressions while showing less agreement with highly informal or unconventional forms. This suggests that students' attitudes are not indiscriminate but are instead shaped by considerations of appropriateness, familiarity, and perceived acceptability within formal domains.

In summary, these findings highlight the complex and layered nature of language attitudes among future educators. Philippine English appears to be both accepted and valued, particularly within local and educational contexts, yet its broader application remains subject to selective evaluation. This nuanced positioning underscores the importance of examining not only whether a language variety is accepted, but also the conditions under which it is considered appropriate for use.

The findings of this study revealed that instructional supervision at Minglanilla Central Elementary School was consistently practiced and positively perceived by teachers. Teachers reported that activities such as classroom observation, feedback, and mentoring were regularly implemented and helpful in enhancing their instructional practices and overall performance (Garcia & Weiss, 2021; OECD, 2022). The respondents also demonstrated a high level of teaching performance, excelling in lesson delivery, classroom management, and learner engagement, reflecting the effectiveness of supervision as a professional support mechanism.

Furthermore, correlational analysis indicated a significant positive relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' teaching performance, suggesting that consistent and supportive supervision contributes directly to improved instructional practices. These results align with findings that collaborative and constructive supervision promotes teacher growth and effectiveness, particularly in delivering learner-centered instruction (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2021; Li et al., 2022). In the Philippine context, this underscores the importance of strengthening supervisory mechanisms to meet diverse learner needs and maintain high-quality education (DepEd, 2023).

The results of this study indicate that instructional supervision plays a significant role in enhancing teachers' teaching performance at Minglanilla Central Elementary School. The consistent implementation of supervision activities, such as classroom observation, feedback, and mentoring, was positively perceived by teachers and contributed to high levels of lesson delivery, classroom management, and learner engagement. These findings align with research showing that effective supervision improves instructional practices and overall performance (Garcia & Weiss, 2021; OECD, 2022).

In the Philippine context, the study underscores the importance of strengthening instructional supervision to address diverse learner needs and maintain quality education in basic schools (DepEd, 2023). When supervision is collaborative and supportive, it fosters professional growth and encourages teachers to adopt more engaging, learner-centered approaches (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2021; Li et al., 2022). Overall, these results highlight that strategic and consistent supervision is a key factor in promoting teacher effectiveness and improving student outcomes.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the attitudes of undergraduate language students toward Philippine English across four dimensions: experiences, observations, perspectives, and future recommendations, as well as their acceptance of selected grammatical and lexical features. The findings indicate that students generally hold favorable attitudes toward Philippine English, recognizing it as a legitimate language variety and associating it with Filipino identity. Moreover, Philippine English appears to be actively used in both academic and everyday contexts, reflecting its functional role in students' linguistic experiences.

However, the results also reveal a more nuanced pattern of acceptance. While students express strong agreement regarding the legitimacy and cultural value of Philippine English, their support is comparatively moderate when considering its broader application beyond local or educational settings. Similarly, although most grammatical and lexical features are accepted, respondents demonstrate selectivity by showing lower agreement toward less conventional or highly informal forms. These patterns suggest that students' attitudes are shaped not only by familiarity but also by considerations of appropriateness and context.

The findings of this study have important implications for language education, particularly in teacher preparation programs. As future educators, students' generally positive attitudes toward Philippine English may influence their openness to incorporating localized language forms in classroom instruction. At the same time, the observed selectivity highlights the need for a balanced approach that acknowledges Philippine English as a legitimate variety while maintaining awareness of standard forms used in wider communication contexts.

In light of these findings, it is recommended that language education programs provide clearer guidance on the role of Philippine English in instruction, including its appropriate use alongside other English varieties. Further research may explore broader populations and employ more rigorous sampling techniques to enhance generalizability, as well as investigate how language attitudes translate into actual teaching practices.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data underlying the findings of this study may be obtained from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. Access will be granted in line with ethical standards and measures to ensure participants' confidentiality.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.